
Learning to See Sharper: A Physics-Informed Artificial Intelligence Framework for Super-Resolving Galaxy Spectra

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Abstract

1 The scientific information recoverable from galaxy spectra is fundamentally set
2 by the resolution, yet assembling large high-resolution samples remains obser-
3 vationally expensive. We present a three-stage physics-informed deep-learning
4 framework for spectral super-resolution that enhances *James Webb Space Tele-*
5 *scope* (JWST)/Near Infrared Spectrograph (NIRSpec) low-resolution prism spectra
6 ($\mathcal{R} \sim 100$) by a factor of ~ 10 in resolving power ($\mathcal{R} \sim 1000$), recovering medium-
7 resolution detail from prism-only observations. Trained on 1,187 paired *JWST*
8 *Advanced Deep Extragalactic Survey* (JADES) observations, our model achieves
9 noise-limited residuals across most of the 1–5 μm range and systematically im-
10 improves the signal-to-noise (S/N) of key diagnostic emission lines, such as [O II],
11 H β , [O III], and H α , often by factors of several. The architecture embeds spec-
12 troscopic physics directly: a dedicated redshift-inference head provides global
13 spectral context, while a line-token self-attention branch parameterizes individual
14 emission features as Gaussian profiles constrained by physical inter-line relation-
15 ships. The framework can be extended to forthcoming wide-field grism surveys
16 (*Euclid*, *Roman Space Telescope*), enabling population-level diagnostics across
17 millions of galaxies otherwise inaccessible at low resolution.

18 1 Introduction

19 The physical information encoded in galaxy spectra is gated by observed resolution. From redshifts
20 and star-formation rates to gas-phase metallicities and active galactic nuclei (AGN) diagnostics,
21 the richest spectroscopic diagnostics require well-resolved line features. Emission lines close in
22 wavelength such as H α /[N II], the [O III] $\lambda\lambda 4959, 5007$ doublet, blend irretrievably at low resolution,
23 biasing every downstream physical quantity extraction (Faisst et al., 2018; Agostino et al., 2023).

24 Modern wide-area missions face an inherent tension between survey volume and spectral quality.
25 Space observatories such as *Euclid* and the *Roman Space Telescope* will deliver grism spectroscopy
26 for tens of millions of galaxies at $\mathcal{R} \sim 100\text{--}300$, far below what resolves fine diagnostic lines at
27 many redshifts (Laureijs et al., 2010; Spergel et al., 2013). Targeted programs such as JADES with
28 JWST/NIRSpec provide exquisite medium-resolution data but cover far fewer targets.

29 One way to circumvent this trade-off is to leverage the small but growing number of galaxies observed
30 at both low and high spectral resolution, and use machine learning to learn the mapping between
31 the two, enabling the resolution enhancement of the much larger low-resolution samples. Machine
32 learning has found broad application in astronomical data analysis (Hemmati et al., 2022; Sanjaripour
33 et al., 2024; Parker et al., 2024), yet spectral resolution enhancement remains largely unexplored.
34 The model is trained on paired spectra from the *JWST Advanced Deep Extragalactic Survey* (JADES;

35 Eisenstein et al. 2023), where low-resolution observations are matched with medium-resolution
 36 spectra of the same galaxies.

Figure 1: Example paired JWST/NIRSpec spectra for a representative JADES galaxy ($z = 3.235$). The prism (red) covers $0.6\text{--}5.3\ \mu\text{m}$ at $\mathcal{R} \sim 100$; the three medium-resolution ($\mathcal{R} \sim 1000$) grating segments (G140M, G235M, G395M; green, blue, black) are overplotted. Vertical dashed lines mark key emission lines at the galaxy’s redshift. The prism blends features that the gratings can resolve.

37 2 Data: Paired JWST/NIRSpec JADES Spectra

38 Our training dataset is drawn from the JADES dataset Eisenstein et al. 2023; Bunker et al. 2024;
 39 D’Eugenio et al. 2025; Curtis-Lake et al. 2026), conducted with the NIRSpec instrument. JADES
 40 observes the same galaxies in both the prism disperser ($\mathcal{R} \sim 100$, $0.6\text{--}5.3\ \mu\text{m}$) and three medium-
 41 resolution grating modes (G140M, G235M, G395M; combined $1\text{--}5.5\ \mu\text{m}$, $\mathcal{R} \sim 1000$), providing
 42 naturally co-observed paired spectra. An example of the prism and medium-resolution spectra for a
 43 representative JADES galaxy is shown in Figure 1.

44 **Pre-processing.** Sources observed in both modes are cross-matched by sky position (separation
 45 $< 0.2''$) and field name. The three grating spectra are merged into a single continuous reference
 46 by minimizing root mean square (RMS) flux differences in overlap regions and applying consistent
 47 flux scale factors. Both prism and stitched grating spectra are placed on a common wavelength
 48 grid defined by the native grating sampling; the prism is up-sampled via cubic interpolation, which
 49 preserves broadband shape without introducing artificial structure. Galaxies are retained only if their
 50 medium-resolution spectrum shows $S/N > 5$ in at least one of $H\alpha$, $[O\ II]$, or $[O\ III]$, yielding **1,187**
 51 **paired spectra**.

52 **Augmentation.** Each pair generates 20 stochastic realizations via Gaussian redshift offsets ($\sigma_z = 0.3$)
 53 and 10% flux perturbations, yielding 24,927 augmented pairs that promote shift-robust, noise-tolerant
 54 learning.

55 3 Physics-Informed Super-Resolution Framework

56 Our pipeline comprises three sequentially trained components; Figure 2 shows the overall design.

57 **Stage 1 — Coarse Super-Resolution (SR1).** SR1 is a 1D residual convolutional neural network
 58 that maps the prism spectrum x_{pr} to an initial super-resolved estimate x_{sr1} and a predicted log-
 59 variance $\log \sigma_{\text{sr1}}^2$. It is trained with a heteroscedastic negative log-likelihood loss that reflects the
 60 wavelength-dependent noise of the NIRSpec detector. The architecture uses ~ 8 residual blocks with
 61 small convolutional kernels and hidden dimension ~ 128 , providing a physically plausible spectral
 62 backbone on which subsequent stages operate.

63 **Stage 2 — Redshift Inference (ZHead).** ZHead is a 1D CNN applied to the SR1 output that infers a
 64 redshift estimate \hat{z} and its uncertainty $\log \sigma_{\hat{z}}^2$. Treating redshift as an explicit global latent parameter
 65 captures long-range spectral coherence that local convolutions cannot encode: line pairs relevant
 66 to one another (e.g., $[O\ III]\ \lambda\lambda 4959, 5007$ and $H\beta$) may be separated by hundreds of pixels in the
 67 observed frame. During SR2 training, a teacher-forcing schedule linearly decays the probability of
 68 substituting the catalog redshift for \hat{z} from 0.8 to 0.2, transitioning the model from supervised to
 69 self-consistent redshift inference.

70 **Stage 3 — Physics-Informed Residual Refinement (SR2).** SR2 predicts a residual correction
 71 $\Delta x = \Delta x_{\text{line}} + \Delta x_{\text{CNN}}$ to the SR1 output via two parallel branches.

72 *Line-token self-attention branch.* For each of $K = 20$ known rest-frame emission lines, a local
 73 spectral window around the expected observed-frame wavelength at \hat{z} is encoded by a small CNN into
 74 a compact feature vector; a learnable species embedding distinguishes morphologically similar lines.
 75 The K tokens are processed by a Transformer encoder, enabling every line to exchange information

Figure 2: Three-stage super-resolution architecture. **SR1**: a 1D ResNet-CNN maps the prism spectrum to a coarse super-resolved estimate and predictive uncertainty. **ZHead**: a 1D CNN infers the galaxy redshift \hat{z} from the SR1 output. **SR2**: a two-branch residual refiner conditioned on \hat{z} , combining a line-token self-attention branch (parametric Gaussian profiles per emission line) with a convolutional branch for smooth continuum correction.

76 globally. This explicitly encodes physical inter-line relations ($\approx 1:3$ [O III] doublet ratio, Balmer
 77 decrement) inaccessible to local convolutions. Each token decodes into a parametric Gaussian profile;
 78 a redshift-conditioned wavelength mask suppresses outputs where no feature is expected.

79 *Continuum correction branch.* A shallow ResNet-CNN with scaled skip connections ($\times 0.5$) predicts
 80 smooth continuum deviations Δx_{CNN} , biased toward low-frequency adjustments. The two-branch
 81 design physically decomposes the galaxy spectrum into discrete emission features plus a slowly
 82 varying continuum.

83 **Hyperparameter Optimization.** We performed three sequential Bayesian sweeps using Weights
 84 & Biases (Biewald, 2020), with a total of $\sim 100,000$ trials, exploring learning rate, weight decay,
 85 dropout, hidden dimension, residual blocks, and activation per stage; SR2 additionally covered
 86 attention heads/layers, spectral window width, and L1 amplitude penalty. Optimal values across all
 87 stages consistently favor exponential linear unit (ELU) activations, learning rates $\sim 10^{-4}$, and ~ 8
 88 residual blocks.

89 **Computational resources.** All stages were trained on a single **NVIDIA RTX 3090** (24 GB VRAM);
 90 final models require 2–4 hours per stage, with the full Bayesian sweep costing ≈ 400 GPU-hours.
 91 The pipeline totals $\approx 2.5\text{M}$ parameters; inference takes < 1 s per spectrum.

92 4 Results

93 We evaluate performance on the 20% held-out evaluation set.

94 **Spectral reconstruction.** Figure 3 shows example reconstructed spectra for two held-out galaxies.
 95 SR2 resolves the [O III] $\lambda\lambda 4959, 5007$ doublet into two peaks at the correct flux ratio ($\approx 1:3$) while the
 96 prism input shows only broad, blended features. Residual analysis confirms that SR2–high-resolution
 97 (HR) residuals are noise-limited: the robust scatter $\sigma_{\text{resid}}(\lambda)$ converges to the median HR noise
 98 amplitude $\tilde{\sigma}_{\text{HR}}(\lambda)$ above $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$.

99 **Emission-line S/N improvement.** For each galaxy and diagnostic line, we fit a Gaussian model
 100 $f(\lambda) = C_0 + C_1\lambda + A \exp[-(\lambda - \mu)^2/2\sigma^2]$ to the low-resolution (LR) and super-resolved (SR) spec-
 101 tra, computing $S/N = A/\delta A$ from the fit covariance. Figure 4 shows that for all four key diagnostics,
 102 the majority of galaxies lie above the one-to-one relation, confirming systematic improvement. These
 103 gains translate into higher-fidelity emission line detection and thus more precise estimates of the
 104 physical characteristics of the galaxy.

105 **Redshift consistency as a downstream diagnostic.** Identical redshift-inference networks trained
 106 on LR, SR, and HR spectra show SR reduces the normalized median absolute deviation [NMAD;
 107 $|\Delta z|/(1+z)$] by $\approx 50\%$ relative to LR, cutting the outlier fraction from $\sim 16\%$ to $\sim 12\%$ (Figure 5).

Figure 3: Example super-resolution outputs for two held-out JADES galaxies. Low-resolution prism input (red dashed), super-resolved SR2 output (orange), and medium-resolution reference (purple) over the full 1–5 μm range. Insets zoom into the [O III] $\lambda\lambda 4959, 5007$ showing deblending of features entirely unresolved at prism resolution.

Figure 4: Emission-line S/N (LR vs. SR) for [O II], $H\beta$, [O III], and $H\alpha$. Points above the one-to-one line indicate improvement; color encodes \log_{10} density.

Figure 5: Predicted vs. true redshifts for LR (left), SR2 (middle), and HR (right) networks. SR2 substantially reduces scatter and outlier fraction, approaching the HR oracle. The true redshifts are obtained from the medium-resolution JADES spectral catalog.

108 5 Discussion and Conclusion

109 We have presented a physics-informed deep-learning framework that achieves noise-limited spectral
 110 super-resolution of JWST/NIRSpec galaxy spectra. By embedding spectroscopic domain knowledge
 111 (e.g., redshift inference, line-token self-attention, and a two-branch refinement stage) the model
 112 recovers spectroscopic information consistently with underlying physics. The downstream scientific
 113 impact is substantial: improved S/N enables higher-fidelity Baldwin-Phillips-Terlevich (BPT) dia-
 114 grams Baldwin et al. 1981, star-formation rate densities, and gas metallicity gradients. The broad
 115 0.6–5.3 μm coverage makes the framework applicable to *Euclid* and *Roman Space Telescope* grism
 116 surveys delivering spectra for tens of millions of galaxies. Future extensions include incorporating
 117 broadband photometry, expanding the training set through upcoming JWST programs, and applying
 118 the framework to absorption-line features. Physics-informed spectral super-resolution can bridge the
 119 resolution gap between current deep spectroscopic programs and forthcoming wide-area surveys,
 120 enabling population-level diagnostics at a fraction of the observational cost.

121 **Limitations.** The training set of 1,187 spectra introduces mild selection bias toward emission-line
 122 galaxies. Performance degrades at $\lesssim 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ where both prism and HR data are observational noisy.
 123 Transfer to *Euclid* or *Roman* grism data will require domain adaptation for differences in resolution
 124 profile and detector noise.

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418 Question: Are new assets introduced in the paper well documented and is the documentation
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420 Answer: [No]

421 Justification: The trained model and inference code will be released upon acceptance. At
422 submission time, the architecture and training procedure are fully documented in Section 3
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424 Guidelines:

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439 All data are astronomical observations from the JWST/NIRSpec instrument.

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457 No IRB approval was required.

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